

AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION PROCESS AT MYSORE SUGAR COMPANY LTD., MANDYA

¹Dhanalakshmi R, ²Sunil G E

¹Assistant professor, Department of Commerce, STG First Grade College, University of Mysore, Chinakurali, Mandya, Karnataka, India.

² Assistant professor, Department of Commerce, STG First Grade College, University of Mysore, Chinakurali, Mandya, Karnataka, India.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10927131>

Published Date: 04-April-2024

Abstract: Recruitment and selection is the process of determining the requirements for a vacancy, identifying the vacancy and the needs of the person holding the position, advertising the desired position, and selecting the most desirable and qualified candidates. Because human resources are very important in achieving organizational goals and success. Therefore, recruiting and selecting the right person for the right job is important to the success of any organization. The huge value of human capital in an organization gives them a competitive advantage and becomes the lifeblood of the organization. This study examines the complexity of recruitment and selection at Mysore Sugar Company Limited Mandya. This study examines the literature review on the recruitment and selection procedures followed by organizations. This study aims to analyze and explain the recruitment and selection of an organization and how this process affects the overall performance of the organization. It examines the role and importance of human resources in recruitment and explores various aspects that need to be addressed. Think about it. Consider before choosing the people, processes and steps involved in the recruitment and selection process and provide helpful advice on how to operationalize the recruitment process and better career options. The research was conducted using primary and secondary data. A survey was used to collect relevant data from 40 employees. Results are obtained using percentages. Data analysis is done through statistical tools. such as table digraphs. The findings of the study revealed that Mysore Sugar Corporation Limited (Mandya) follows the best recruitment and selection practices, they have career advancement opportunities, they are satisfied with the organization. They are currently eligible to work for and the organization adheres to a fair recruitment policy.

Keywords: Employees, recruitment, selection, recruitment policy, career growth opportunity, job satisfaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Once the number and type of human resources needed are determined, management must determine where customer needs lie and develop strategies to attract them to the organization before selecting competitively. Qualified people for the job. All these processes are often called recruitment. Some people use recruitment time. Theories are not one and the same. Recruiting is just one step in the entire hiring process; some people use the word recruitment to choose. No two words are the same. In other words, the job of recruitment before selection is simply to find resources that will create talented employees and attract them to apply for jobs in the organization. Selection is the process of finding attractive candidates. Now the topic of recruitment. We will be looking at recruitment throughout our lives. Recruitment is the process of identifying potential candidates and encouraging them to apply for current or potential positions. The recruitment process is best based on defining the job, the job and the characteristics of existing employees, allowing us to plan financially or prepare our employees to perform the work in terms of volume. Talent Recruiting provides a pool of highly motivated

candidates. So, knowing who we need and how many people we want to hire, we can choose from available candidates. It provides greater flexibility and greater control over the development process. In addition to providing equal opportunities for employees during the recruitment process, employers also need to ensure a good relationship between employees and the business. Selection refers to the process of selecting people with the necessary skills to work in an organization. The only option is to choose the best candidate. It tries to strike a good balance between what the client can and wants to do and the needs of the organization. Recruitment and selection are often viewed as a process. Effective recruitment and selection can help organizations maximize productivity by selecting the best candidates quickly and cost-effectively. But good studying and selection can be costly and time-consuming. But recruitment and selection are still important for business because failure and selection will cause the business to fail.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

1 Kumari et al (2010),

Kumari et al.'s research shows that the company follows a clear hiring policy. Often, companies reimburse employees for expenses incurred. It was found that the company had completely computerized all its databases. All employees said the company hired consultants or recruiting agencies to find candidates. Despite some oddities, it can be said that the company has been in good shape since the beginning. The conclusion from the above research is that the performance of the company all 120 employees says that the company manages and manages competitive information, including data processing to enable the collection of competitive information. 70 out of 120 employers said their companies spend 20% to 30% of their total budget on recruitment and selection. All 120 employees confirmed that Coca-Cola followed the recruitment and selection process. This depends on the role the candidate is applying for and most companies will reimburse the employee for any expenses incurred. 70 out of 120 employers said the company reimbursed workers for expenses paid, while 50 employers said that all 120 employers managed company administration and tender documents, including keeping records to ensure bidders filled out information completely.

2 Price (2007),

In this study, human resources management views recruitment and selection as the process of finding and attracting potential employees for employment. He said the hiring process is not a simple selection process but requires management decisions and extensive planning to select the most qualified people. There is a competition between businesses to find the most talented employees on the road to innovation, and management decisions and employers try to recruit candidates who best suit the company's culture and ethics. This reflects the fact that management will select candidates who can meet the requirements of the role they are applying for, including teamwork, because teamwork is essential for every position.

Kumari (2012),

Kumari's research shows that recruitment and selection strategies improve performance. In similar cases, the research was designed to shed light on recruitment and selection issues. The primary objective is to identify common practices used by organizations to recruit and select employees and to determine how employee selection and selection processes impact the operations of SMC Global Securities Limited. The search method adopted will be a search. The data was collected through well-structured questionnaires. As per the study, out of the various methods of sourcing candidates, the best one is- getting references via references and networking. In the process, he came across various experiences where the role of HR and the relevant traits he found in the candidates were displayed The structure of the financial sector is known and the analysis shows that recruitment is an ongoing activity in the business world and requires new and innovative methods thought of and applied to meet the demand. Companies should focus on long-term consistent performance rather the short term. More emphasis should be placed on training and improving recruitment.

Daly et al (2003),

Their research shows that Australia's workforce diversity has increased over the past 25 years, driven by increased immigration, particularly from South East Asia. Although many immigrants have knowledge, skills and abilities before entering the country, most immigrants face significant problems with finding a good job with these skills. This article is an investigation into the recruitment and selection preferences of managers, recruitment professionals and expats in selected Australian cities. Problems with the recruitment and selection of diverse employees. However, it is also accepted that the study has some limitations, such as the small sample size. Although observing more participants would have been ideal. It should be acknowledged that this was a small study and therefore exploratory in nature. Additionally, immigrants' reported differences in place of residence may not moderate the impact of culture on job performance.

Ayesha Tabassum (2011),

Tabassum conducted an assessment and evaluation of the current recruitment and selection process and made some recommendations that could help Basic Bank leverage its human resources to their full potential, especially in the future. The nature of this research paper is case study based. Temel The bank has a human resources department responsible for all recruitment and selection activities. The bank is free to choose from many candidates as it is more important for external recruitment agencies. Such hiring practices eliminate political and personal bias. However, since internal staffing is cheaper and less time-consuming than external staffing, banks need to try to balance internal and external staffing based on the type of work, time and money. Basic Bank can use employee referrals for recruitment to increase employee retention. Promotion and change will ultimately focus on improving performance, but will also help improve employee morale and leverage external resources. Recruitment sites, recruiting schools, workplaces, workplaces, etc. BANK will be presented with many options. Such as. Finally, analysis of current recruitment and selection policies will lead to future opportunities for Temel Bank, because the purpose of recruitment and selection is to select people who compete best for the job, the organization, and the conflict therein. It can incur costs an organization spends a lot of money, time and effort, which ultimately affects employee retention and the performance of the organization.

Jahan (2012),

A study has been carried out to create a good public service which is necessary for the effective implementation of public policies and the provision of public services. To create an effective public service, the government must ensure that talented, skilled and motivated people work in the public service. Therefore, recruitment and selection must be objective, consistent and effective. But it is very sad that there is no full public service in Bangladesh. Being efficient in public appointments is essential to a good public service. However, in our recruitment policy, no attention has been paid to effective selection due to three basic problems in the recruitment and selection of the BCS. The first of these is the quota law. There is a huge disagreement between eligibility and fairness standards in formulating BCS recruitment and selection policy, the latter being the flawed examination process. Politics and corruption lead to poor choices and weak staff. Political views and participation in these activities have a significant impact on the quality of the public service and increase confidence in the recruitment process. As a result, bright candidates rarely hold public office and the BCS program has been destroyed. If there is competent management in recruitment and selection, and there is political and service spirit, we can make the office efficient, strong and have a strong management. It is a more respectful country.

Jackulin. M. (2011),

A study shows that Wipro Technologies is one of the largest information services companies in the world. Wipro provides IT solutions and services including integration, data outsourcing, packaging, implementation, software development and maintenance, and research and development to businesses worldwide. There are many departments in Wipro where the HR department plays an important role compared to other departments. Recruitment and selection are very good at Wipro. The company's sources of recruitment are very effective. The main source of internal recruitment is employee referral as rewards are provided to employees to encourage this kind of recruitment. Recruitment is a never-ending process in the organization. Selecting qualified and skilled candidates is the main motto of the organization. The excellent pattern of interview is followed in the case of the selection process. The Candidates' eligibility verification program is a greatest merit to the organization to unfaithful candidates in the organization. The systematic procedure is to follow unfaithful candidates in the organization. The recruitment and selection process follows a standard process.

Silzer (2010),

However, the recruitment process does not end with searching for candidates and selecting the right candidates. But as Silzer said, it's about managing staff and keeping them selected. Silzer's work focuses on talent management and through his studies; he addresses questions Such as whether talent is something innate or something that can be developed, and the process of development. According to Silzer et al., this is a challenge that organizations and senior managers face when developing technology. The only solution is to adopt a complete recruitment process, and companies that follow the recruitment process face significant problems with its implementation, regardless of whether they have the skills and cooperation of the management team to choose the right way to hire. Therefore, although companies should use their internal management to apply general theory widely in specialist organizations, human resource management theory can provide insight into the best recruitment methods.

Dickie and Dickie (2009),

In their research, they found that many countries or local companies entering the Chinese market cannot easily transfer or acquire these resources. This article compares Western HR practices with Chinese culture. An important finding is that while similar dimensions are used to describe HR processes, culture influences practices differently. There are many similarities between recruitment and selection by Australian and Chinese companies. On the face of it, the recruitment and selection processes used in the two countries represent a test of the HR policies, strategies and procedures developed, tested and implemented by multinational companies. But while the recruitment and selection process is no different from the words used to describe it, it is important to understand candidates' limitations and responsibilities for leadership in cultural institutions and broader societies. Therefore, each country's approach is very different. In both countries, workers' understanding of the world is based on education that reflects reality. Fortunately, this isn't a problem when people follow well, common sense, and good techniques.

Gopalia (2011),

This article uses Tesco as an example to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the use of the Internet to recruit and select talent. Online recruiting is very effective in saving on recruitment and selection costs. Research on the effectiveness of online recruiting and selection shows that it saves recruiting time and reduces recruiting costs. This study investigated the effectiveness of online recruitment and selection. Research Tesco and draw conclusions. Research shows that online recruiting can help save hiring costs, shorten time to hire, help companies achieve better results, improve corporate image and love good skills. Online recruiting also appears to be effective in managing the talent process. According to research, e-recruitment will increase in the coming years. Using an online recruitment and selection process has the advantage of economies of scale. Therefore, this feature of e-recruitment will attract many companies to invest in the development of e-recruitment products. Only a few researchers have examined the impact of online recruitment and selection processes. For this reason, a lot of research is now being done focusing on the growth of the economy.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. The objective of this study is to analyze and interpret the recruitment and selection process of Mysore Sugar Company, and how the process results in overall efficiency of the organization.
2. To analyze the role and importance of the human resources department in recruiting an employee.
3. To find out various essential factors that should be considered before selecting the person.
4. To know the process and steps involved in the recruitment and selection process.
5. To make valuable suggestions on how to make the process of recruitment and selection more effective.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The success of the research study depends on the methodology adopted for the study. Methodology means the science of methods used by the researcher to collect, analyze and present information.

And methodology is a collection of information which is restored through primary and secondary data, interviewing customers and discussing with personnel, going through past records, files of the organization's journals, books etc.

A descriptive study has been carried out in order to solve the problem and find suitable solutions to the primary and secondary objectives to determine the effectiveness of the recruitment and selection process of the employees.

In order to procure the necessary data, a survey has been conducted in the various departments of the company

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

1. PRIMARY METHOD

Primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire. In the questionnaires, questions are presented with exactly the same wording and exactly the same order to all respondents. The reason for standardization, of course, is to ensure that all respondents are replying to the same questions. The questionnaire was personally handed over to the targeted respondents in order to elicit the right responses.

QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

The questionnaire was formulated and designed by the investigator through the help of the personnel department in accordance with the objectives of the study.

A structured questionnaire with a view to collecting the requisite information was prepared. Open ended dichotomous questionnaire, multiple choice questionnaire, check list (respondents having a series of answers from which they choose) etc.

SAMPLE

The questionnaire was administered for a filed survey in Mysore sugar company ltd., Mandya with a sample size of 40.

2. SECONDARY METHOD

Secondary data was collected from journals, textbooks, articles, and internet websites.

5. THEORYTICAL FRAMEWORKS

Meaning of human resource management

Human resources play an important role in the development of the economy. **ARTHUR LEWIS** observed & quit; Great Differences in the development of countries with similar resources require the study of differences in human behavior & quit. Human resource management is the management of employees' skills, knowledge, skills, intelligence, creativity, talent, etc., Management. There are different concepts for managing people. These are labor management, labor management, labor management, worker-employee relations, industrial relations, management people, human rights management, etc. Although these terms can be used broadly, there are differences between resources or services and the access. Evolutionary stage. In simple terms, human resource management means hiring people, developing, utilizing, managing their resources and paying for their services according to the needs of the business and organization.

RECRUITMENT

Recruiting means "finding" external employees. Recruiting has long been considered the most important part of the HR function because even the best planning, design and management won't mean much if employees are hired. Recruitment means identifying potential applicants that the organization orders. Therefore, the aim of recruitment is to find people suitable for the job and specific tasks. Its definition is "the pursuit of human resources based on the implementation of effective measures for the preparation of employees and the promotion of adequate talent in order to facilitate the selection of good talent."

Yodele pointed out that recruitment is a process of finding talent. Human Resources is to meet the needs of the employee and to encourage people with sufficient skills by using the right measures and to facilitate the selection of good employees

Edwin B Flippo defines recruitment as "the process of finding potential employees and encouraging them to apply for jobs in an organization." "It is the process of finding and attracting qualified employees. The process begins with the hiring of new employees and ends with the submission of applications. The result is the selection of new employees for the applicant."

SELECTION

Selection is a passive process that involves eliminating candidates who do not have the skills and qualifications required for the job. It is also the process of discriminating among applicants to identify and hire those most likely to be successful on the job. The purpose of the selection process is to select the person who can do the job best among qualified candidates. Determining whether a candidate's qualifications are suitable for a particular job and Recruitment is a process and process adopted by a particular company. The selection process or job usually follows a standard model, starting with a preliminary interview. And end with the final decision. The usual selection process includes: preliminary interview, completed application, performance test, general interview, background check, physical exam, and finally, placement decision. Today, every organization should consider employee preparation as one of the most important activities. Human resource planning is by far the most important thing for the long-term success of any organization. There are many strategies that every organization must follow to ensure that it has the right number and type of people in the right place at the right time to help

the organization achieve its planned goals. In general, the objectives of the human resources planning department include resources, planning, recruitment and selection, career planning, training and development, promotion, risk management, performance measurement, etc. takes place. Each of these goals must be carefully considered and planned accurately and successfully. It is important for every organization to hire the right people for the right positions. Recruitment and selection play an important role in this. Step-by-step analysis of recruitment and selection, as uncertainty and the rapid spread of new technologies put great pressure on employers to recruit and select jobs. This article provides an in-depth review of past literature on recruitment and selection processes in the current context. This article is mainly based on the analysis of six documents prepared by experts and researchers in the field of human resource management. Many scholars have contributed to human resource management by providing profound and in-depth knowledge of branches of human resource management such as search and selection, human resource management, medical job review, recruitment needs and objectives.

6. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRITATION

Data analysis was done based on the survey results. Data is expressed as percentages. The opinions of the sample participants were analyzed and presented in graphics and words, and are presented on the following pages.

Table 1: AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Category	No of The Respondents	Percentage (%)
20-30	5	12.5%
30-40	10	25%
40-50	25	62.5%
Total	40	100%

Source: Field survey

The above table shows that of 40 employees, 62.5% belong to the 40- 50 age group, 25% of the employees ranging from 30-40 age groups, only 12.5% of the employees belong to the age group of 20- 30 years.

Table 2: GENDER (SEX) OF THE RESPONDENTS

Gender	No Of The respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	34	85%
Female	6	15%
total	40	100%

Source: Field survey

An attempt was made to ascertain the gender of the respondents related to study. From the above table, it is found that 34 of the respondents constituting 85% are male and 6 of respondents constituting 15% of the total are female.

Table 3: Marital status of the respondents

Category	No of the respondents	percentage
Married	25	62.5%
Unmarried	15	37.5%
total	40	100%

Source: field survey

The above table shows that 62.5% of the respondents are married, 37.5% of the respondents are unmarried.

Table 4: Qualification of the respondents

Category	No of the respondents	percentage
SSLC	5	12.5%
PUC	15	37.5%
DEGREE	20	50%
TOTAL	40	100%

Source: field survey

In the company, around 12.5% of employees have SSLC as an education qualification, 37.5% of employees have PUC as an education qualification and 50% of the employees have a Degree.

Table 5: BEST SOURCES FOR RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION PROCESS

OPINION	NO.OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Internal	15	37.5%
Consultants	10	25%
Print	10	25%
Others	5	12.5%
Total	40	100%

Source: field survey

From the above table, it can be shown that 37.5% of the respondents preferred internal sources as the best sources for the recruitment and selection process, 25% of the respondents prefer consultants, 25% of the respondents are of the opinion that they recruit through print media, and 12.5% are of the opinion that the company recruits from other sources.

TABLE 6: METHODS OF SELECTION

OPINION	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Written test	18	45%
Medical test	0	0%
Interview	22	55%
Other	0	0%
Total	40	100%

Source: - Field source.

The above table shows 45% of respondents satisfied with the written test method of selection, but 55% of respondents were satisfied with an Interview using the method of selection.

TABLE 7: METHODS USED FOR RECRUITMENT

OPINION	NO.,OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Structure	16	40%
Unstructured	8	20%
Case study question	14	35%
Others	2	5%
Total	40	100%

Sources :- Field survey.

From the above chart shows that 40% of the sample respondents responded that the company recruits the workers from structured and 20% of sample respondents responded that the company recruits the workers from unstructured and 35% of the opinion that the company recruits the employees from case study questions and 5% of the opinion that the company recruits the employees from others.

TABLE 8: SATISFIED AT PRESENT JOB

OPINION	NO,OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Yes	35	87.5%
No	5	12.5%
Total	40	100%

Source :- Field survey.

The above table shows that 87.5% of respondents are satisfied with the present job and 12.5% of respondents are not satisfied with present job.

Table 9: CAREER GROWTH OPPORTUNITY

Opinion	No ,of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	23	57.5%
No	17	42.5%
Total	40	100.0%

Source :- Field survey.

The above chart shows that 57.5% of the respondents are satisfied with the career growth opportunity and 42.5% of the respondents are not satisfied with the career growth opportunity.

Table 10: METHODS OF RECRUITMENT DO YOU USE FOR YOUR RECRUITMENT

Methods	NO.OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Employees referrals	10	25%
Govt employment exchange	0	0%
Advertisement in local /nation paper	25	62.5%
Professional journals	0	0%
Recruitment constants	5	12.5%
Total	40	100%

Source: - Field S

From the above table or chart, it is clear that 25% of the respondents said that employee referrals are used as a recruitment method and 62.5% of the respondents said that advertising in local national paper is used as a recruitment method and the remaining 5% of the respondents said that recruitment constants to identify the respondents is used a method of recruitment.

TABLE 11: THE PERCENTAGE OF WEIGHTAGE DO YOU THINK THE COMPANY HAS GIVEN TO THE FOLLOWING FACTORS IN YOUR SELECTION.

Opinion	No ,of respondents	Percentage
Aptitude test	5	12.5%
Personal interview	18	45%
Written test	12	30%
Practical test	5	12.5%
Total	40	100%

Source - Field source.

From the above chart, it is clear that 45% of the respondents are of the opinion that personal interview tests are given more weight and 30% of the respondents are of the opinion that written tests will help as a factor of selection according to the company's remaining 10% of the respondents responded that aptitude test and practical test is given weight as a selection factor according to company.

Table 12: THE IMPORTANT THING YOU LOOK WHILE SCREENING RESUME OF CANDIDATES.

opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Qualification	7	17.5%
Experience	10	25%
Communication skill	3	7.5%
Attitude	20	50%
Total	40	100%

Source- Field

The above chart shows that 17.5% of the respondents are of the opinion that qualifications are viewed as the important thing while screening the candidates, and 25% of the respondents are of the opinion that experience is viewed as the important thing while screening the candidates and 7.5% of the respondents are of the opinion that communication skill is viewed as the important thing while screening of candidates remaining 50% of the respondents are of the opinion that attitude is important.

Table 13: THE PRESENT RECRUITMENT POLICY IN ACHIEVING GOALS OF THE COMPANY

Opinion	No ,of Respondents	Percentage
yes	33	82.5%
No	7	17.5%
total	40	100%

Source - Filed survey.

From the above table, 82.5% of the sample respondents opined that company recruitment policy is helping in achieving the goals of the company and 17.5% of the sample.

Table 14: SUGGEST SHOULD BE SOURCES OF FORECASTING.

OPINION	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Total cost of the project	0	0 %
Past experience	15	37.5%
Different phases of the project	5	12.5%
All the above	20	50%
Total	40	100

Source - Field Survey.

From the above table, it can be shown that 50% of the respondents perceive that their company is forecasting on the basis of all the above, 12.5% of the respondents are of the opinion that a company is forecasting on the basis of past experience, and the remaining 37.5% opinion that the company forecasting on the basis of different phases of the project.

Table 15: THE RECRUITMENT POLICY OF THE ORGANIZATION.

Opinion	No. of respondents	Percentage
good	30	75%
bad	10	25%
total	40	100 %

Source - Field survey.

The above table shows that 75% of the respondents have a good opinion about the recruitment policy of the organization, while 25% of the respondents have a bad opinion about the recruitment policy of the organization.

Table 16: RECRUITMENT & SELECTION PROCESS INCREASE EFFICIENCY IN THE ORGANIZATION ACTIVITIES

Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	10	25%
Strongly Agree	5	12.5%
Disagree	15	37.5%
Strongly disagree	5	12.5%
Neutral	5	12.5%
Total	40	100%

Source :- Field Survey.

The table shows that 25% of the respondents agree that efficiency in the organized activities, while 37.5% of the respondents disagree with the above statement. And 12.5% of respondents strongly agree that there is efficiency in the organization's activities. And 12.5% of respondents strongly disagree; the remaining 12.5% of respondents responded that as neutral. Hence, it is clear that the recruitment and selection process increases the efficiency of the organization's activities.

7. FINDINGS

- In the study found that most of the employees nature of work is now technique
- Most of the employee's opinion with the present job gives career growth opportunity.
- Most of the employees are satisfied with present job.
- Almost all employees are satisfied with the interview test.
- Majority of the employees are satisfied with the advertisement methods of recruitment.
- Majority of the employees are satisfied with recruitment policy.
- Most of the employees are satisfied with the communication flow in organization.
- Most of the employees are opinion that recruitment and selection process increase efficiency in the organization.

8. SUGGESTIONS

- Employee participation in recruitment programs should be given importance.
- Along with recruitment programs, employees have to go to other technological advanced plants on a visit to sharpen their skills.
- Provide more opportunities for career and personal growth through training, education and more challenging assignments.
- Conduct periodical feedback surveys on recruitment to know the current trend in the market.
- Besides pay and promotions, they create a good working environment and a healthy environment to work in.
- The selection process should be less time-consuming.
- During the selection process, not only the experienced candidates but also fresh candidates should be selected so as to avail the innovation and enthusiasm of new candidates.
- Evaluation and control of recruitment and selection is given.
- Recruitment programs have to be organized aiming at overall personality development of each individual employee.
- Technological gradation is the order of the day, so pertinent recruitment programs have to be organized.

9. CONCLUSIONS

Today's highly competitive business environment makes it difficult for organizations to find, hire and select talent. As the number of qualified workers decreases, competition for talent increases. The scarcity of applicants makes it even more important for organizations to attract, select and retain the right candidates. The results of this study suggest that organizations should offer attractive salaries to attract qualified candidates. Depending on the number of jobs currently available, job seekers have options when searching for their ideal job. They are looking for more than an attractive salary. Candidates are looking for organizations that offer a variety of benefits, advancement opportunities, and an environment where they can learn and grow. If the organization cannot provide these, job seekers will find an organization that does. Therefore, organizations must fully understand how attractive They are to potential employees and highlight their best qualities when selecting candidates. Once organizations complete the candidates, they must select the best potential the job based on the decision. Organizations use many tools to help them select people. Project reports deal with all organizations and selection processes that are an integral part of any organization. Recruitment reflects each applicant's skills, abilities and experience. Options include creating a list of qualified candidates, developing a selection strategy, identifying qualified

candidates, evaluating qualified candidates, and selecting the most qualified candidates. The results of this study suggest that selection tools designed to collect information about candidates' behavior and motivations can help make good choices. For example, behavioral interviewing is a popular selection activity among organizations with highly effective selection systems. In the future, many organizations plan to use these and similar tools in employee selection. Organizations know that having good, legal and strong work can help them select the right people for the right job: Many organizations are ready to use a variety of tools to the fullest and invest heavily in this process. Workers can benefit from the following benefits if they railways looking for qualified workers. Reduce employee turnover. Increased productivity leads to economic benefits. Reduce maintenance. Global competition and the survival of the fittest in the global economy are ensured through the recruitment process. Finally, better recruitment and selection strategies can improve organizational performance. The more they do this, the more they will find and retain talent, which will impact the core business of production and financial performance. So invest in understanding. Ignorance, illness and disease are three major challenges for healthcare workers. There must be conflict in the family, in society, in the workplace, and between work groups. They have to fight on every front.

So, in the context of "NAHI GNANENA SADRUSHAM" it means that there is nothing comparable to wisdom . This is true!

REFERENCES

- [1] Kamran, A., Dawood, J., & Hilal, S. B. (2015). Analysis of the recruitment and selection process. In *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Management Science and Engineering Management* (pp. 1357-1375). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [2] Shailashree, V., & Shenoy, S. (2016). Study to identify the relationship between recruitment, selection towards employee engagement. *Study to Identify the Relationship between Recruitment, Selection towards Employee Engagement. International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME), ISSN (Online), 2455-5630.*
- [3] Bhoganadam, S. D., & Rao, D. S. (2014). A study on recruitment and selection process of Sai Global Yartex (India) private limited. *International Journal of Management Research and Reviews, 4(10), 996.*
- [4] Bahuguna, P. C., & Kumari, P. (2010). Strategic Human Resource Management & Organizational Performance. In *Pervasive Computing for Business: Trends and Applications* (pp. 150-165). IGI Global.
- [5] Daly, A. J., Barker, M. C., & McCarthy, P. C. (2005). Preferences in recruitment and selection in a sample of Australian organisations.
- [6] Dickie, C., & Dickie, L. (2005). Recruitment and selection processes in Australia and China: rewards from common sense and plain dealing. In *Tenth Cross-Cultural Research Conference, Hyatt Dorado Beach Resort and Country Club, Puerto Rico* (pp. 11-14).
- [7] Gopalia, A. (2012). Effectiveness of online recruitment and selection process: a case of Tesco. *World Applied Sciences Journal, 20(8), 1152-1158.*
- [8] Kumari, G., Bhat, J., & Pandey, K. M. (2010). Recruitment and Selection Process: A Case Study of Hindustan Coca-Cola Beverage Pvt. Ltd, Gangyal, Jammu, India. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology, 1(4), 441.*
- [9] Jahan, M. (2012). Recruitment and selection process in Bangladesh civil service: A critical overview. *Public Policy and Administration Research, 2(5), 29-36.*
- [10] Tabassum, A. (2011). The process of recruitment and selection in a developing country: Case study of a bank in Bangladesh. *ABAC Journal, 31(1).*
- [11] Kumar, S., & Gupta, A. K. (2014). A study on recruitment & selection process with reference. *Int J Res, 1, 1661-1666.*
- [12] Rozario, S. D., Venkatraman, S., & Abbas, A. (2019). Challenges in recruitment and selection process: An empirical study. *Challenges, 10(2), 35.*

- [13] Thorat, T., & Jagtap, M. (2022). Analytical study of HR recruitment process. *International Research Journal of Humanities and Interdisciplinary Studies (IRJHIS)*, 197-206.
- [14] Gomathy, D. C., Ramaseshacharyulu, M. A., Sarath, M. C. S., & Sreekanth, M. A. S. (2022). Overview of recruitment and selection process in hrm. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Engineering and Management (IJSREM) Volume, 6*.
- [15] Alzoubi, R. (2020). The recruiting process in the human resource management. *International Journal of Recent Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 7(1), 65-71.
- [16] Nanor, A., Owusu, E., Senyah, M. M., Owusu, E. K. O., & Agyei, S. K. (2022). Recruitment and Selection Policies and Procedures and Their Effects on Organizational Performance: A Case Study. *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 35, 405.
- [17] Naveen, S., & Raju, D. N. M. (2014). A study on recruitment & selection process with reference to three industries, cement industry, electronics industry, sugar industry in Krishna DtAp, India. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 15(5), 60-67.
- [18] Hsu, Y. R., & Leat, M. (2000). A study of HRM and recruitment and selection policies and practices in Taiwan. *International Journal of human resource management*, 11(2), 413-435.
- [19] Djabatay, E. N. (2012). *Recruitment and Selection Practices of Organisations: A Case Study of HFC Bank (Gh) Ltd* (Doctoral dissertation).
- [20] Gomathy, D. C., Kiran, M. A. S., & Karthik, C. A. (2022). The Recruitment Policies and Procedures in Organizations and Companies. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Engineering and Management (IJSREM) Volume, 6*.
- [21] www.hr-survey.com
- [22] www.google.com
- [23] <http://www.iiste.org/journals/index.php/IEL/article/view/1079>
- [24] <http://www.Pbr.coin/brochure/0002.pdf>.
- [25] <http://www.Journal.Av.Educe/abackjournal/2011/Jan2011/05-process.pdf>.